

Quantifying Urban Attractiveness: The Role of Spatial Configuration and Visual Metrics in Perceived Attractiveness

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Summary

Understanding what makes urban scenes visually attractive is essential for designing cities that enhance well-being and walkability. This study takes a quantitative approach, moving beyond qualitative assessments, to evaluate how spatial configurations and visual characteristics shape perceived attractiveness. Using more than 1,800 urban images and ratings from 24 participants, we analyzed metrics like spatial configuration of objects, textural features, and structural attributes. Findings show these metrics effectively capture the attractiveness of areas through imagery. This framework provides designers with a valuable tool to evaluate and refine their designs, offering actionable insights to enhance urban aesthetics and livability.

KEYWORDS: urban attractiveness, urban aesthetics, visual metrics, urban greenery, computational urban analysis

1. Introduction

Urban aesthetics and attractiveness play a crucial role in shaping human experiences and perceptions of city environments (Ewing & Handy, 2009; Subiza-Pérez et al., 2019). Beyond mere visual appeal, aesthetics and attractiveness influences the livability, functionality, and emotional connection individuals form with urban spaces (Chen et al., 2024; Tuan, 1977). The inclusion of natural elements, such as greenery, has been shown to play a critical role in enhancing urban attractiveness, offering restorative benefits and fostering positive emotional responses (Frumkin et al., 2017; Jahani & Saffariha, 2020; Malekzadeh et al., 2023). Moreover, creating attractive urban areas is linked to well-being, economic vitality, and social cohesion (Hoyle et al., 2017; Pazhouhanfar & M.S., 2014). As cities continue to grow and evolve, understanding what makes a space aesthetically pleasing is vital for designing environments that are both engaging and sustainable.

The determinants of urban quality and attractiveness have become well established by an interdisciplinary research community, including urban planners, architects, environmental psychologists, and geographers. This body of work highlights the interplay between physical features, spatial configurations, and perceptual factors (Ewing & Handy, 2009). Various theories highlight how design qualities shape human interactions with urban spaces, including Kevin Lynch's (1960) imageability, Christopher Alexander's (1977) pattern languages, legibility (Evans et al., 1982; Lynch, 1960), transparency (Arnold, 1980; Ewing & Handy, 2009), complexity and coherence (Rapoport, 2013), and human scale and linkage (Craig et al., 2002; Gehl, 1987; Moudon & Lee, 2003).

While these conceptual frameworks provide a strong foundation, they are often qualitative in nature,

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relying on subjective assessments or theoretical interpretations. Our study takes a quantitative approach to address this gap, aiming to systematically evaluate urban attractiveness through measurable metrics derived from street-level imagery. By leveraging spatial configuration indices along with texture-based metrics, we seek to quantify the visual and spatial qualities that contribute to perceived urban attractiveness. Our method bridges established theories with data-driven analysis, offering new insights into how urban design elements can be optimized to create visually and functionally superior cityscapes.

2. Methodology

We acquired panoramic Google Street View (GSV) images from Helsinki using the Google Maps API. Images, collected between 2009 and 2017. Panoramic 360° images were composed of six directional images (0°, 60°, 120°, 180°, 240°, and 300°). To ensure comprehensive spatial coverage, 1000 random locations were sampled, supplemented by images from key locations identified in a walkability survey conducted by the City of Helsinki (Norppa & Hovi, 2020). The final dataset included 1,967 images, evaluated by 24 participants, with each participant providing an average of 1,014 ratings, resulting in a total of 24,349 ratings. Participants rated the images on a scale from 1 (completely unappealing) to 7 (completely appealing). Semantic segmentation of these images was performed using the InternImage model (Wang et al., 2023) with the UperNet architecture (Xiao et al., 2018), pre-trained on the Cityscapes dataset (Cordts et al., 2016), to classify pixels into distinct semantic categories. Segmentation was executed on a high-performance computing system, producing detailed pixel-level classifications for subsequent analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. An example of semantic segmentation analysis demonstrates the classification of image features. Some features were removed or combined in our analysis due to presence of multicollinearity.

We employed a range of metrics to quantify spatial configuration and visual properties of the images (Table 1). Spatial metrics such as patch density, edge density, density of greenery, and proximity index assessed the distribution and interaction of elements like greenery, buildings, and roads. To examine image texture, two Haralick Texture Features—contrast and angular second moment (ASM)—were derived from the gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM), quantifying visual properties like complexity and smoothness (Haralick et al., 1973). Fractal dimension was also calculated to quantify the self-similarity and complexity of urban patterns. These properties can capture subtle visual cues that human observers may associate with aesthetic quality and attractiveness, complementing spatial metrics.

Table 1. Overview of selected metrics with brief definitions.

Metric	Definition
Patch* Density	Number of patches over total number of pixels (scaled).
Proximity Index	Mean distance to the nearest patch of the same class.
Edge Density	Boundary length of patches over total number of pixels (scaled).
Haralick ASM	Sum of squared probabilities in the co-occurrence matrix.
Haralick Contrast	Measures local intensity variation in the GLCM.
Fractal Dimension	Box-count exponent reflecting spatial complexity of shapes.

*A contiguous group of pixels belonging to the same class in the image.

To account for the observed complexity and non-linear patterns in the data, we applied an optimized random forest model (maximum depth of 20, square root selection of features, a minimum of four samples per leaf, a minimum split size of 10 samples, and 200 estimators) to investigate the relationship between quantitative metrics and participant-rated attractiveness. The importance of each feature was determined using the permutation feature importance method, which quantifies a feature’s contribution by analysing the reduction in model accuracy when its values are randomly altered (Altmann et al., 2010). To visualize how the features influence perceived attractiveness scores, we utilized accumulated local effects (ALE) plots (Apley & Zhu, 2020).

3. Results

The random forest model achieved a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.49 for the training set and 0.34 for the test set in explaining attractiveness rated by the participants. The root mean squared error (RMSE) was 0.7 for the training set and 0.8 for the test set. To provide a clearer understanding of the variables used in the model and their variation across different urban environments, Table 2 presents the values of the key metrics for three representative images.

Table 2. Metrics for three representative urban images, including spatial configuration indices and visual texture metrics, illustrating variability in urban composition and aesthetic characteristics. Due to the size constraints, the images have been cropped, and certain portions are not displayed here.

Metric			
Patch Density			
Built Environment	3.64	6.87	1.14
Greenery	1.97	1.66	2.91
Terrain	1.04	2.70	0.41
Sky	1.35	0.10	0.31
Proximity Index			
Built Environment	0.16	0.09	0.04
Greenery	0.03	0.04	0.15
Terrain	0.14	0.04	2.21
Sky	0.38	0.00	1.06
Edge Density (Greenery)	1.15	0.52	0.25
Density of Greenery	0.69	0.07	0.03
Haralick ASM	0.19	0.84	0.95
Haralick Contrast	0.88	0.22	0.27
Fractal Dimension	1.68	1.86	1.78

The permutation feature importance analysis reveals the most influential variables driving the model's predictions, and the ALE plots provide detailed insights into how these variables are linked to perceived attractiveness through SVIs (Figure 2 and 3). Haralick contrast, the most significant variable, shows a strong positive relationship with perceived attractiveness. This suggests that higher variations in pixel intensity, reflecting complex textures, are associated with more visually appealing urban environments. The density of greenery demonstrates a positive relationship with attractiveness, underscoring the crucial role of natural elements in shaping favourable urban perceptions. Haralick ASM exhibits a predominantly negative relationship with attractiveness in the ALE plot, indicating that smoother and less complex textures might be less appealing in urban settings. This complements the importance of textural richness observed in the contrast feature. Lastly, edge density of greenery shows a positive effect on attractiveness.

Figure 2. Permutation feature importance showing the contribution of each variable to the model's predictions. Negative values reflect random variations or noise introduced during the permutation process.

Figure 3. Accumulated local effects (ALE) plots, based on standardized values, illustrate the relationship between key variables and perceived attractiveness.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Our findings reinforce existing urban design theories, particularly those emphasizing the interplay between visual richness, greenery, and overall spatial organization in shaping positive human responses (Ewing & Handy, 2009). By quantitatively linking textural variation with aesthetic preference, this study offers fresh support for earlier conceptual models—such as including Kevin Lynch’s (1960) imageability, and Christopher Alexander’s (1977) pattern languages—that identify complexity and memorability as integral to human-scale urban experiences. The consistency between these theoretical constructs and our data-driven outcomes indicates that complexity is not simply a subjective impression but can be systematically captured and analysed using advanced computational tools.

An important insight emerging from our work is the multifaceted role of greenery. While many have underscored the benefits of natural elements in urban contexts (Poom et al., 2021), our approach adds

nuance by showing how both the extent of greenery and its spatial configuration interact to enhance visual appeal. This complements prior qualitative findings on the psychological and restorative impacts of green infrastructure, but further positions greenery as a core design parameter that can be carefully optimized in both new developments and urban retrofitting.

Likewise, the results reveal the subtle influence of texture features. Haralick metrics, often employed in image processing, here become conceptual levers that decode how fine-grained variations in urban surfaces resonate with human aesthetic judgments. This helps reconcile the longstanding debate around “ordered complexity,” where the right balance of coherence and visual interest can stimulate positive affect (Boeing, 2018). By translating texture metrics into actionable design guidelines, future urban interventions could focus on micro-level articulations—like facade treatments, materials, or vegetation patterns—to enrich perceived urban attractiveness.

Finally, the predictive modelling approach extends beyond correlational analyses by offering interpretable feature importances. This data-driven angle not only pinpoints influential visual elements but also opens possibilities for scenario testing. Urban planners and designers can simulate the effect of modifying specific parameters—such as increasing green edge density—before undertaking costly interventions. Thus, our method operates as an integrative bridge, uniting computational precision and novel AI methods with human-centred design goals.

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